

ROLE OF BLOCKCHAIN IN COLLABORATIVE DDoS MITIGATION

ABHINAV BHANDARI

Department of Computer Science & Engineering, (Punjabi University), Patiala, India.
Email: bhandarinitj@gmail.com

ASHOK KUMAR BATHLA

Department of Computer Science & Engineering, (Yadawindra Department of Engineering), Talwandi Saboo, Bathinda. Corresponding Author Email: ashokashok81@gmail.com

Abstract

One of the most serious security threats to network domains is a distributed denial of service attack. Various mitigation mechanisms are widely deployed in various networks or domains, but they lack the resources and resilience to deal with DDoS attacks on their own. Collaborative mitigation systems have been developed to improve the DDoS mitigation capability of a single mitigation system by exchanging mitigation information. However, for collaborative DDoS mitigation architectures, deployment complexity, secure information exchange, and trust remain issues. Block chain technology has recently demonstrated its compatibility with fields such as supply chain management, health care, IoT, and other public services. Because Block chain is distributed in nature and effective in data integrity and transparency, it can integrate with collaborative DDoS mitigation systems. This paper provides an overview of the integration of Collaborative DDoS mitigation systems with Block chain technology. We discuss the history of DDoS mitigation and Block chain, as well as the applicability of Block chain to collaborative DDoS mitigation and open challenges in this area.

Keywords: Block chain, Security, Trust, Data sharing, Cooperative Defense, Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS)

1. INTRODUCTION

The Internet has evolved into a necessary component that has a significant impact on our daily lives. The majority of users rely on the Internet for most services such as financial, shopping, healthcare, and education. Emerging megatrends such as cloud computing, social networking, mobile computing, and big data necessitate greater bandwidth and speed than ever before. There is a hasty growth in the number of unsafe devices which are estimated to be more than 50 billion by the end of 2020 [1]. This rapid growth can make things easier for the attackers who want to disturb the essential network services, so network security has become a crucial requirement. One of the active attacks called Denial of Service (DoS) has been impacting the network services for many years and still, it is still a major challenge. Denial of service (DoS) attacks is one of the key reasons for affecting the accessibility of the network services. First DoS attack happened in 1974 and since then these attacks have gained in frequency, power and complexity. The strength of this attack becomes more when launched in a distributed manner (called Distributed Denial of Service attack).

In Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attack target machine resources become unavailable for legitimate users [1]. Even though it is a very well-known attack it is still considered a major concern for big organizations or service providers. The hasty increase in the number of unsafe devices lets the malicious users take control over a large number of unsafe or unsecured devices

to launch an attack. It became difficult for internal defense systems and cloud-based defense systems due to transmission bottleneck and centralized tactics. DDoS attack is distributed in nature so a distributor and collaborative mitigation solution would be a better option for defending against the DDoS attack. Some literature shows the numerous advantages of collaborative mitigation or defense systems against DDoS attacks [2]–[6]. It basically combines the abilities of the different participants in a collaborative defense to reduce the mitigation burden on a single node or network and helps to block the attack traffic near to its origin. Even though there are so many advantages of collaborative mitigation solutions, no extensive deployment of these collaborative and cooperative mitigation solutions due to lack of efficiency and deployment complexities or difficulties. The main challenges of existing mitigation solutions are high deployment complexity, high complexity of cooperation and coordination between two participants, trusted communication and incentive scheme for cooperation [7], [8].

Some of the new technologies like SDN and Block chain recently showed potential in this area due to the special features of these technologies. Block chain technology is moving towards different types of areas as Block chain works in a distributed manner without a trusted intermediary unlike in centralized systems [9]. Things can be done in a decentralized way without the help of the central authorities. Block chain technology could play a major role in collaborative DDoS mitigation services due to its key features like pure distributed and well-secured in nature. For example, in sharing malicious IP among the different domains with help of Block chain network which is an immutable platform. The main objective of this paper is to confer the likelihood of combining collaborative DDoS mitigation with Block chain technology. We introduced the background of DDoS mitigation and challenges in Collaborative DDoS mitigation. Keeping a view on collaborative DDoS mitigation, we introduce the background of Block chain and its applications and then provide a perception on where Block chain technology can be useful for addressing the problem of Collaborative DDoS Mitigation.

The enduring part of this paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the background of Block chain technology and its applications. Section III presents the background of DDoS Mitigation and major challenges. We discuss how Block chain technology can be integrated with DDoS mitigation for solving problems in existing DDoS mitigation solutions in Section IV and discuss open challenges in section V. Finally, Section VI concludes the work.

2. BACKGROUND OF BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY

In recent times, Cryptocurrency drew widespread attention from both education and industry. Bitcoin is referred to as the Cryptocurrency and has a major achievement in the market in the year 2016. Block chain is the basic technology behind Bitcoin. Block chain was proposed in 2008 and in 2009, it was put in practice [9]. The Block chain is like a public ledger in which all validated transactions are collected in a series of blocks. The chain expands persistently when fresh blocks are added to it. This new technology has major features like decentralization, persistence, secrecy, audibility. The Block chain operates in a decentralized environment that

has the capability to combine many essential technologies like cryptographic hashes, asymmetric cryptography and distributed consensus algorithms. Block chain is cost-effective and more efficient because it works in a decentralized model. Though Bitcoin or any Cryptocurrency is one of the key applications of the Block chain, it has much potential in other miscellaneous applications other than the cryptocurrencies. Block chain is going to play a major role on the internet for the future.

A. Characteristics of Blockchain

With some analysis efforts [10] [11] [12] [13] some basic characteristics of Block chain as described below as:

1. **Distributed:** Block chain is designed as a distributed system that works in point-to-point networks. This makes it ideal for organizational business networks in which there is heavy dealing among the different types of organizations. Each user within the network needs to validate transactions and has a uniform copy of the ledger. After that encrypted transactions can be added. If any change takes place in a ledger that would mirror all its copies in a very short time.
2. **Immutability:** Once all nodes unite about a transaction and then it is recorded after verification, it cannot be modified again. You can only change the state of a transaction by doing the same process again but cannot modify the previous transaction. one should not be able to hide the original transaction. He can trace any asset throughout its life. So, all the valid transactions are practically changeless because of the necessity for verification by all different nodes within the network.
3. **Consensus:** An agreement is required to validate the block or transactions. If all the members of Block chain are agreed only then block or transaction is accepted. All the members should conform to the same agreement. A transaction that does not follow the same agreement won't be accepted.
4. **Irreversible:** Block chain is irreversible as Hashing is used so it would be complicated and it's not possible to reverse it. It is not possible to drive a private key from the public key. Even one modification within the input could lead to a totally different hash.

B. Types of Blockchain

Block chain can be categorized into three types based on access permissions i.e. Public Block chain, Consortium Block chain, and Private Block chain [14][15].

Public Block chain: In public Block chain, every node can read, add transactions and conjointly engage within the consensus process. A public Block chain is totally transparent and decentralized. Bitcoin or Ethereum are some examples of public Block chains.

Consortium Block chain: In consortium Block chain, just some node that is selected in a pre-defined way can participate in the consensus process. Only specific nodes can be read. Block

chain can also be public or restricted thus we are able to say it's partially decentralized. Hyperledger is an example of Consortium Block chain. Private Block chain: In private Block chain one central node having to write permission and read permission are often public or restricted. Most private companies are using private Block chain for their desired purpose.

Table 1: Comparison among Public block chain, Consortium Block chain and Private Block chain

Property	Public block chain	Consortium block chain	Private block chain
Consensus determination	All miners	The selected set of nodes	One organization
Read permission	Public	Could be public or restricted	Could be public or restricted
Immutability	Nearly impossible to temper	Could be tempered	Could be tempered
Efficiency	Low	High	High
Centralized	No	Partial	Yes
Consensus process	Permission less	Permissioned	Permissioned

C. Smart Contract

The smart contract came into existence in the 1990s as a transactional protocol that is computerized and executes automatically the contract terms of an agreement [16]. These are built on top of the Block chain and these are like triggers imposed automatically when a condition is fulfilled. The trigger will execute the matching function automatically after condition fulfilment in a smart contract. For example, person A and person B agree on the fine for breaching the agreed contract. Suppose person A disrupts the contract, penalty (as mentioned in the contract) is automatically deducted from the account of person “A” and credited to the account of person “B”. A Smart contract has the following phases during its life cycle as shown in fig.2 [17]

- 1. Creation:** The first phase is to create a smart contract and it can be done by several rounds of discussions on the rights prohibitions on the contract among participant parties [30]. Parties may take the help of counselors and lawyers to draft the first copy of the agreement and then the software developer creates a smart contract from the written agreement like in other software development. All participant parties, stakeholders, counselors, lawyers and software developers are involved in the whole process.
- 2. Deployment:** When a software developer creates a smart contract then these are validated and installed on the top of the Block chain. Once the deployment of the smart contract on the Block chain is done it cannot be altered due to the property of the Block chain. For any kind of modification in the existing contract, the only way is to create a fresh smart contract and install it on the Block chain again.
- 3. Execution:** All the clauses present in a contract are being observed and checked when any trigger condition occurs the corresponding function in a smart contract executed automatically.

- 4. Completion:** After the execution of any function from the smart contract corresponding to a particular condition matching, new situations of involved participants are updated and stored on a Block chain.

D. Major Applications areas of Block chains

Figure 1: Life Cycle of a smart contract [17]

It would be sensible to say that Block chain technology is one of the most pioneering revolutions. In the beginning stage, everybody related it to Cryptocurrency and Bitcoin, but this opinion is changing now. The potential of Block chain technology is spreading too many other areas due to its special properties like decentralization and transparency. Some of the key application areas of the Block chain are given below as:

- 1. Finance:** The first application of Block chain is in the Finance sector. In recent years it has created a massive impact on old-style monetary services, and it has the ability to upset traditional banking systems. Block chain technology may be useful in areas in the financial domain. Companies like Microsoft and IBM are taking step-up and are going to provide Block chain-as-service. Some of the open areas of Block chain applications are there like organization transformation, point-to-point financial market, risk management.
- 2. Internet of things (IoT):** The hasty increment in IoT devices with diversity has created problems with scalability, security, efficiency, and accessibility. Even though IoT is still humming along, it is facing problems in deployment. The two rising technologies SDN and Block chain will play the main role in solving deployment problems with IoT networks. Block chain could be used in applications of IoT like smart homes, e-health, smart grids and has the potential to improve the IoT services. There is the scope of Block chain technology in the e-business model for IoT and security of IoT.
- 3. Public services:** Block chain may be employed in public services like energy-saving, education, Land registration. Block chain can even be widely employed in public and social services. Physical assets like land could be registered on the Block chain and all related tasks can be recorded and handled on the public Block chain.it would increase the

efficiency of the service. Block chain technology could be useful in the online education sector.

4. **Reputation system:** Reputation is the way of evaluation by which someone trusts you. The truthfulness of someone is directly proportional to the reputation means more the reputation more the trust. For example, the reputation of an individual can be measured by his historic dealings and interactions. Reputation systems can be applied in areas like e-commerce, academics and web communities.
5. **Security:** Block chain technology could be applied to security enhancement and privacy concerns. In recent times, security and privacy are major issues or challenges because of the increase in vast no of unsafe devices. By looking at the special characteristics of Block chain technology it could have great potential to tackle these rapidly rising challenges.

3. BACKGROUND OF DDOS MITIGATION

DDoS mitigation is all procedures or techniques required for resisting or mitigating the effect of distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks on different networks by defending the victim and pass on networks. The task of the first phase of DDoS mitigation is to recognize normal network traffic conditions by defining patterns used for threat detection and warning [2]. DDoS mitigation needs to identify incoming traffic to separate the illegitimate traffic from legitimate traffic. Once the detection is done the next thing is to filter traffic by processes like IP reputation lists, blacklisting/whitelisting or rate-limiting [18]. In general DDoS mitigation approaches, Rate-limiting is used where access to a website or service is blocked if excessive requests come from the same IP. After the threshold limit, IP is not able to access a website or service. In the same sense, there is a way to block the group of IP addresses that are relevant to each other through an address matching method. One another approach may be based on geographic anomalies. It validates the information of requests, IP addresses and geography to identify odd requests. Numerous procedures have been projected to mitigate DDoS attacks. Present DDoS mitigation approaches can be categorized into two classes: Intra-domain DDoS mitigation and Inter-domain DDoS mitigation (shown in figure - 1) [7].

Figure 2: Classification of Mitigation Techniques

a) Intra-domain DDoS mitigation

The mitigation schemes which work within an autonomous system or domain. Many intra-domain DDoS mitigation techniques have been proposed using different approaches like filtering packets, flow-based IDS, Open sketch. A filtering scheme that verifies valid packets provides a solution against IP-spoofing attacks was proposed in [7] but it was not able to handle real source IP-based attacks. Rodrigo et al. Proposed an IDS scheme by using the OpenFlow protocol to collect traffic flow information [19]. Yu et al. proposed a software-defined traffic measurement scheme called OpenSketch which offers an effective technique to gather measurement data across a three-phase channel, which are hashing, filtering, and counting. It has a drawback of overloading the control plane [20]. Wang et al. proposed an entropy-based detection scheme but it is not able to find the victim for blocking it [21]. K. Giotis et al. merged sFlow with Open flow protocol for detecting DDoS attacks which actually reduce the extra communication burden among the data plane and control plane. El houda et al. proposed DDoS mitigation technique with help of software-defined networks (SDN) which includes schemes like Intra Entropy-based scheme to measure the randomness of data inside the domain using sflow, Intra Bayes-based scheme [7] to differentiate flows which are not legitimate using entropy and an intra-domain Mitigation system to mitigate flows which are not legitimate inside the domain [7].

b) Inter-Domain mitigation

DDoS attacks are growing swiftly and becoming more disturbing day by day. To handle such kind of big-scale DDoS attacks, cooperation among the different domains or autonomous systems has become essential for effective mitigation. The Internet has a dynamic nature so defense which is based on a local domain is not very effective therefore, collaboration among all domains becomes necessary in order to handle DDoS attacks.

Some collaborative mitigation procedure has been proposed to deal with any kind of DDoS attacks. It is not an easy task to implement these due to their complexity and limited efficiency. Guo et al. Proposed a technique which installs filters at the boundary of the network to stop arriving packets with source IP addresses that do not belong to the network. This proposal requires a different ISP to take part in providing the list of valid IP addresses. IETF proposed a new protocol called DOTS (DDoS Open Threat Signaling) for sharing DDoS attacks information [22]. The execution of the inter-domain DDoS mitigation method can be either distributed or centralized. In [3], Steinberger et al. Proposed a similar kind of scheme like [22]. It simplifies collaboration between different domains by using flow-based format. Some other inter-domain DDoS mitigation methods using SDN, NVF technologies have been proposed. By summarizing all we can conclude that it is hard to implement these proposed methods due to some issues like complexity, trust and cost. B. Rodrigues et al. [8] have come up with a new signaling system called Block chain signaling system (BloSS). It was basically the practical implementation of the architecture proposed in [23]. The use of Block chain technology increases the efficiency of the signaling system, as compared to the previous existing signaling systems like DDoS Open Threat Signaling (DOTS). Signaling systems like DOTS required

some specialized kind of hardware for its operation. BloSS does not require any kind of special type infrastructure for its operation which reduces its operational cost. Z. A. El Houda et al. [7] have proposed Cochain-SC, a Block chain-based approach, which includes intra-domain and inter-domain DDoS mitigation. In intra-domain, they proposed DDoS mitigation techniques with help of software-defined networks (SDN). For inter-domain, they proposed a collaborative DDoS mitigation scheme using Block chain by using smart contracts. They proposed a smart contract-based framework for collaboration between different SD-based domains by using Ethereum's smart contract. It is the only scheme for providing both levels of mitigation i.e. intra-domain and interdomain DDoS mitigation.

Mitigating DDoS attacks and sustaining the accessibility of services is a complicated task and some actions are required from the upstream level because the victim does not always have the resources to mitigate the attack. Huge resources are required from upstream networks as DoS attacks involve a gigantic amount of malicious traffic. So a collaborative mitigation approach becomes necessary for an effective mitigation solution but collaborative mitigation suffers from many issues. Some of the major issues in collaborative DDoS mitigation approaches are as follow:

- Mitigation for a large volume of DDoS attacks handling the huge volume of malicious traffic.
- Prevention of infrastructure damages so that the legitimate user can have access to service.
- Mitigation process should be implemented using existing infrastructure without the need for some specialized infrastructure.
- To keep the mitigation, process up to date for the latest attacks.

Recently, the focus of researchers is on Block chain in the wide range of industries which was initially restricted only to cryptocurrencies. Block chain technology is moving towards different types of areas as Block chain works in a distributed manner without a trusted intermediary unlike in centralized systems. Things can be done in a decentralized way without the help of the central authorities. Block chain technology could play a major role in DDoS mitigation services due to its key features which are desirable in collaborative DDoS solutions.

4. BLOCK CHAIN-BASED DDOS MITIGATION

In this section, we elucidate the challenges encountered in collaborative DDoS Mitigation and discuss the applicability of Block chain technology.

a. Challenges in collaborative DDoS Mitigation

Even though DDoS mitigation has been studied for a long time, sharing of data and trust factor in a collaborative or cooperative DDoS mitigation are still main challenges.

1. Sharing of data or information: In collaborative DDoS mitigation systems sharing of data and information is one of the major challenges or issues. No one is ready to share data or

information due to lack of trust. So, without availability of information or data from all the participants, it is not possible to build an effective collaborative DDoS mitigation model to mitigate a large-scale DDoS attack.

2. Trust Factor: Trust among all the participants is one of the major factors in any kind of collaborative system. The trust computation is required to measure the level of trust among all the nodes or participants. In collaborative mitigation systems, it is a major issue. Solutions for the trust computation are mostly centralized and the central server can be compromised.

3. Deployment complexity: In collaborative DDoS solutions another important factor to be considered is the complexity in implementing the collaborative DDoS mitigation solution among all the participants or networks, which may differ in many ways by their nature. To set up a whole new infrastructure for collaborative DDoS mitigation would be very costly. It is a big challenge for the collaborative DDoS mitigation solutions to decrease the implementation complexity somehow.

b. Block chain-based solutions

Block chain technology is moving towards different types of areas as Block chain works in a distributed manner without a trusted intermediary unlike in centralized systems. Things can be done in a decentralized way without the help of the central authorities. Block chain technology could play a major role in DDoS mitigation services due to its special features which are suitable for collaborative DDoS mitigation. Major components of collaborative DDoS mitigation as Block chain-based solutions are shown in figure-3.

Figure 3: Major components of Collaborative DDoS Mitigation for Block chain-based solution

1. Sharing of data or information: Trust and privacy are the two major factors if someone is thinking of data or information sharing. These two factors are considered by all the participants in the collaborative DDoS mitigation system, which are essential because participants do not want the information they share to be used for malicious purposes. Block chain is one of the solutions that will help to reduce or mitigate this big data sharing challenge. Participants in collaborative solutions may make an information-sharing agreement signed by each of the

participants in collaborative DDoS mitigation solutions. All this would be on Block chain and publicly available to all the participants which is unalterable. For privacy of the data, it can be renovated before sharing or can be secreted by any way and all this information is shared as a transaction on Block chain. In general, Block chains can be very useful in sharing the data or information by preserving trust and privacy of data.

2. Trust Factor: Trust is the main factor in collaborative DDoS mitigation systems and to compute the trust of a particular node or participant in a collaborative DDoS mitigation system is still a big challenge due to many factors like false reporting, fraud rating etc. Block chain technology offers a robust system to mitigate the issue of computing trust issues. An efficient algorithm for the trust factor can be built over the Block chain as a smart contract which would be public and unalterable.

3. Deployment complexity: A collaborative DDoS mitigation system would be a distributed system and spread over many domains. It is a big challenge to deploy this big mitigation system due to the high level of diversity among the different domains participating in the collaborative DDoS mitigation system. Even some special infrastructure and modifications in existing protocols are required which is a very hard task. A public Block chain is an alternative for sharing the information among all the participant nodes as there is no need of setting up new infrastructure. We can use the already existing Block chain network for sharing information by joining the public Block chain network.

5. OPEN CHALLENGES IN BLOCK CHAIN-BASED SOLUTIONS

Block chain technology and Collaborative DDoS mitigation systems complement each other. In spite of this, both have some challenges and limitations which should be solved for making the collaborative DDoS mitigation system more effective.

Cost and energy: To verify the Block chain transaction a lot of computation needs to be done. When we consider the whole Block chain network the computational power enlarges immensely. Some cost is required to complete every transaction so energy and cost involved are still a big challenge.

Security and Privacy: All nodes are the participants in the public Block chain, it is open for all that makes a weak point if considering it as a security and privacy viewpoint. Furthermore, Block chain technology itself could be a target for some cyber-attacks. There is a need to work in the area of security and privacy of Block chain technology.

Acceptance and awareness: Block chain technology is in its early stage and still growing day by day, so it became a big challenge for the Block chain-based mitigation system due to lack of awareness and acceptance. Block chain technology seems to be very complex for all organizations as it is a new emerging technology but success of Block chain-based mitigation solution also depends on how many organizations are adopting this technology. It is a big challenge for any Block chain-based application.

Standards and regulations: Standards and regulations always play a major role in any technology to be adopted by everyone. Block chain is still in its initial phase so standards and regulations are far behind the new emerging technology.

6. CONCLUSION

The Block chain's pure distributed and secure features make it more suitable for collaborative and distributed mitigation against DDoS attacks. Although the integration of Block chain technology with many application areas, such as health care and supply chain management, has been studied, very few efforts have been made to investigate the potential of Block chain technology in collaborative DDoS mitigation. As a result, our efforts primarily confer the applicability of Block chain technology to collaborative DDoS mitigation, as well as challenges or issues. We recognise Block chains' potential for improving collaborative DDoS mitigation systems. There will be a strong need in the future to improve the major components of a collaborative mitigation system, namely data sharing, alert exchange, and trust computation, in order to make the collaborative mitigation system more effective and stronger.

References

1. S. T. Zargar, J. Joshi, and D. Tipper, "A survey of defense mechanisms against distributed denial of service (DDoS) flooding attacks," *IEEE Commun. Surv. Tutorials*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 2046–2069, 2013.
2. G. Loukas and G. Öke, "Protection against denial of service attacks: A survey," *Comput. J.*, vol. 53, no. 7, pp. 1020–1037, 2010.
3. J. Steinberger, B. Kuhnert, A. Sperotto, H. Baier, and A. Pras, "Collaborative DDoS defense using flow-based security event information," *Proc. NOMS 2016 - 2016 IEEE/IFIP Netw. Oper. Manag. Symp.*, pp. 516–522, 2016.
4. W. Li, S. Tug, W. Meng, and Y. Wang, "Designing collaborative Block chained signature-based intrusion detection in IoT environments," *Futur. Gener. Comput. Syst.*, vol. 96, pp. 481–489, 2019.
5. B. Rashidi, C. Fung, and E. Bertino, "A Collaborative DDoS Defence Framework Using Network Function Virtualization," *IEEE Trans. Inf. Forensics Secur.*, vol. 12, no. 10, pp. 2483–2497, 2017.
6. K. Giotis, A. Maria, and V. Maglaris, "A Reputation-based Collaborative Schema for the Mitigation of Distributed Attacks in SDN Domains," in *NOMS 2016 - 2016 IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium*, 2016, no. Noms, pp. 495–501.
7. Z. A. El Houda, A. Hafid, and L. Khoukhi, "Cochain-SC: An Intra- and Inter-Domain DDoS mitigation scheme based on Block chain using SDN and smart contract," *IEEE Access*, pp. 1–1, 2019.
8. B. Rodrigues, T. Bocek, and B. Stiller, "Enabling a Cooperative, Multi-domain DDoS Defense by a Block chain Signaling System (BloSS)," *Semant. Sch.*, p. 3, 2017.
9. H. W. Zibin Zheng, Shaoan Xie, Hong-Ning Dai, Xiangping Chen, "Block chain Challenges and Opportunities : A Survey Zibin Zheng Shaoan Xie Hong-Ning Dai Xiangping Chen Huaimin Wang," vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 1–25, 2017.
10. M. Atzori, "Block chain Technology and Decentralized Governance: Is the State Still Necessary?," *Ssrn*, pp. 1–37, 2016.

11. Z. Zheng, S. Xie, H. Dai, X. Chen, and H. Wang, "An Overview of Block chain Technology: Architecture, Consensus, and Future Trends," Proc. - 2017 IEEE 6th Int. Congr. Big Data, BigData Congr. 2017, pp. 557–564, 2017.
12. M. Pilkington, "Block chain technology: principles and applications," Res. Handb. Digit. Transform., pp. 225–253.
13. Q. Feng, D. He, S. Zeadally, M. K. Khan, and N. Kumar, "A survey on privacy protection in the Block chain system," J. Netw. Comput. Appl., vol. 126, pp. 45–58, 2019.
14. E. Portmann, Rezension „Block chain: Blueprint for a New Economy“. 2018.
15. M. J. W. RENNOCK, A. COHN, and J. R. BUTCHER, "Block chain Technology and Regulatory Investigations," Journal, vol. February/M, no. March, pp. 34–44, 2018.
16. F. Idelberger, G. Governatori, R. Riveret, and G. Sartor, "Evaluation of logic-based smart contracts for Block chain systems," Lect. Notes Comput. Sci. (including Subser. Lect. Notes Artif. Intell. Lect. Notes Bioinformatics), vol. 9718, pp. 167–183, 2016.
17. H.-N. Dai, Z. Zheng, and Y. Zhang, "Block chain for Internet of Things: A Survey," IEEE Internet Things J., pp. 1–1, 2019.
18. K. Kalkan and F. Alagöz, "A distributed filtering mechanism against DDoS attacks: ScoreForCore," Comput. Networks, vol. 108, pp. 199–209, 2016.
19. R. Braga, E. Mota, and A. Passito, "Lightweight DDoS flooding attack detection using NOX/OpenFlow," Proc. - Conf. Local Comput. Networks, LCN, no. October, pp. 408–415, 2010.
20. M. Yu, L. Jose, and R. Miao, "OpenSketch: Software Defined Traffic Measurement," Proc. 10th USENIX Conf. Networked Syst. Des. Implement., pp. 29–42, 2013.
21. R. Wang, Z. Jia, and L. Ju, "An entropy-based distributed DDoS detection mechanism in software-defined networking," Proc. - 14th IEEE Int. Conf. Trust. Secur. Priv. Comput. Commun. Trust. 2015, vol. 1, pp. 310–317, 2015.
22. K. Nishizuka, L. Xia, J. Xia, D. Zhang, L. Fang, and C. Gray, "Inter-organization cooperative DDoS protection mechanism," 2016.
23. B. R. B, T. Bocek, A. Lareida, D. Hausheer, S. Rafati, and B. Stiller, "A Block chain-Based Architecture for Collaborative DDoS Mitigation with Smart Contracts," vol. 10356, pp. 16–29, 2017.